

EFFECTS OF PLAY-BASED APPROACH TO THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF LEARNERS IN GUMACA, QUEZON

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Effects of Play-Based Approach to the Academic Performance of Learners in Gumaca, Quezon

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the Effects of the Play-based Approach to the Academic Performance of Learners in Gumaca Quezon due to the increasing lack of play and the importance placed on direct instruction for learners. To achieve the researcher's goal, the researcher used a questionnaire to determine the respondents' profiles and administered the questionnaire to determine the effects of the play-based approach. This study involved 60 primary teachers from public elementary schools in Gumaca, Quezon. The result showed that most of the respondents were in the age group of 42 years old and above. The respondents are primarily female, and the majority have more than 12 years length of work experience. When it comes to the results of the effects of the play-based Approach, the study found that the most common effect of the play-based Approach on the academic performance of learners is Language Skills Development. According to the result of the Kruskal-Wallis H-test, all the null hypotheses of age, sex, and length of work experience do not vary, which means that there is no significant difference in the perceived effects of the Play-based Approach to academic performance of learners when the respondents are grouped by profile.

Keywords: *academic performance, effects, play-based approach, language skills development*

Introduction

In many countries, there has been a shift towards promoting the use of play-based learning in primary school curricula since the early 2000s. Play-based learning essentially involves learning while having fun. It differs from the broader concept of play. Studies that have examined the benefits of play-based learning have primarily focused on two types of play: free play, which is self-directed by children, and guided play, which involves some level of teacher guidance or involvement.

In Gumaca, Quezon, there are elementary school teachers who have incorporated play into their daily activities. For example, at Gumaca West Elementary School, teachers from Kindergarten up to Grade 3 have introduced and utilized a play-based approach in teaching due to its benefits such as language skills development, problem-solving skills, knowledge retention, and creativity. However, the researcher found issues with Play-based learning curricula that were highlighted by educators in an article, such as difficulty appreciating play's academic significance, lack of formal play-based training, and pressure to use direct instruction to meet predetermined goals.

The researcher is concerned about the increasing lack of play, and the importance placed on direct instruction for learners. With this, the researcher will look into the effects of a play-based approach on the academic performance of learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effects of play-based approach to the academic performance of learners in Gumaca, Quezon. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. length of work experience?
2. What are the effects of a play-based approach to the academic performance of learners with respect to:
 - 2.1. language skills development;
 - 2.2. problem-solving skills;
 - 2.3. knowledge Retention; and
 - 2.4. creativity in performance?
3. Is there a significant difference on the effects of the play-based approach to academic performance of learners in Gumaca, Quezon when respondents are grouped according to profile?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive survey method to collect data on the effects of play-based approach to the academic performance of learners in Lope, Quezon. The researcher used a survey questionnaire as an instrument. Based on the survey's results, the researcher will be able to determine the details of the study.

The descriptive research design is a fascinating scientific approach that enables researchers to observe and describe a subject's behavior

without any influence. (Shuttleworth,2019).

Its main goal is to provide a detailed and accurate "description" of individuals, situations, issues, behaviors, or natural phenomena (Siedlecki, 2020).

Respondents

The study was conducted at Gumaca East Central School and Gumaca West Central School. The respondents were primary teachers, and the researcher chose this school due to its accessibility.

The researcher selected 60 teachers who were teaching in Gumaca, Quezon, in the SY 2023-2024. The study focused on the effects of the play-based approach on learners' academic performance. The respondents were composed of 4 males and 56 females, for a total of 60 teacher respondents.

Instrument

The researcher prepared a researcher-made questionnaire which was validated by two experts. Part I of the questionnaire included the profile of the respondent. Part II of the questionnaire consisted of the effects of play-based approach using the Likert scale of; 5 strongly agree (SA), 4- agree (A), 3- agree (MA), 2- disagree (D), 1- strongly disagree (SD) as perceived by selected primary teachers in Gumaca, Quezon.

To test the internal consistency of the questionnaire using Cronbach's Alpha, a pilot test was conducted at Lopez West Elementary School with 12 respondents. After the computation, the result is 0.96, which is interpreted as acceptable. This means that there is an internal consistency in the prepared research instrument.

Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the principal. Upon approval, the researcher administered the instrument to the target respondents.

In administering the questionnaire, the researcher utilized vacant periods to avoid distractions during class discussions. Teachers were given sufficient time to answer the questions. After collecting the data, the researcher analyzed the results using statistical treatment methods.

The descriptive research method using a Likert scale was used to rate the effects of play-based approach to the academic performance of learners. Data was gathered through "proportionate random sampling." Both male and female primary teachers at Gumaca, Quezon, were selected to fill out the questionnaire. Data was gathered through face-to-face surveys and followed safety health protocols to prevent the spread of the virus.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data will be carefully read and examined for analysis. They will be tallied and entered into a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and Frequency will be used to interpret the profile of the respondents. To test the significant difference of three or more means, the researcher used the Kruskal-Wallis for non -parametric test.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data. All the data gathered were presented here in tabulated form with corresponding interpretations.

The first part described the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and length of work experience. The second part presented the effects of a play-based approach on the academic performance of learners in Gumaca, Quezon.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age*

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
30-32 years old	9	15
33-35years old	7	12
36-38 years old	7	12
39-41 years old	8	13
42 years old and above	29	48
Total	60	100

Table 1 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents based on their age. Close to half (48%) of the respondents are aged 42 years or older, while the remaining 52% fall within the 30-41 age bracket. Specifically, respondents aged 30-32, 33-35, 36-38, and 39-41 make up the latter group.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	4	7
Female	56	93
Total	60	100

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to gender. Seven percent (7%) of them are male, and 93% are female, which indicates that most of the teacher respondents are female.

A study by Sebastian, M., Banate, R., & Saquin, M. (2022) supported this finding, indicating that elementary teaching is still mostly a female-dominated profession. Students have limited encounters with males in elementary education. The study also observed that male and female teachers share equal roles in reproductive, community, and leisure activities.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Length of Work Experience

Length of Work experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
1-3 yrs	3	5	5
4-6 yrs	4	6.7	4
7-9 yrs	7	11.7	3
10-12	12	20	2
More than 12 yrs	34	56.6	1
Total	60	100	

Table 3 displays the frequency and percentage of respondents based on their level of work experience. The data shows that 56.6% of the respondents are teachers who have more than 12 years of experience. On the other hand, 5% of the respondents are teachers who have 1-3 years of experience. Therefore, it can be inferred that the majority of the respondents have extensive teaching experience of over 12 years.

This finding conforms to the study of Puteh, S.R. & Ali, Aliza. (2013). The analysis of the result showed that the duration of teachers' teaching experiences was not the major factor determining teachers' perceptions of the use of play in language and literacy development of preschoolers. It could be argued that the positive response towards play-based education suggests that teachers accept play as being of benefit to the development of children and that the play-based approach will ensure effective learning.

Table 4. Effects of Play-based Approach to the Academic Performance of Learners in terms of Language skills development

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Learners acquire language skills by observing, imitating, and experimenting with peers.	4.75	Strongly Agree
2. My learners learned how to communicate their ideas as they played with their peers.	4.63	Strongly Agree
3. I observed that learners gain knowledge of commonly used words that are integral to everyday communication.	4.67	Strongly Agree
4. I encountered some learners who were able to comprehend instructions	4.57	Strongly Agree
5. My learners acquired and developed language skills such as grammar and rules	4.38	Strongly Agree
Average Mean	4.60	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.0-1.80)", Disagree (1.81-2.60)", Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40)", "Agree(3.41-4.20)", "Strongly Agree(4.21-5.0)"

Table 4 displays the effects of the play-based approach on language skills development. Respondents agreed that learners acquire language skills through observation, imitation, and peer interaction, with a mean score of 4.75. The lowest mean score is for indicator 5, suggesting that learners improve grammar and language rules through the play-based approach. The survey also revealed an average mean score of 4.60, indicating a moderate level of agreement.

Table 5. Effects of Play-based Approach to the Academic Performance of Learners in terms of Problem-solving skills

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Most of the learners become problem solvers.	4.28	Strongly Agree
2. Learners are able to analyze situations if given an activity during guided play.	4.33	Strongly Agree
3. The learners are able to create their own decisions quickly.	4.33	Strongly Agree
4. The learners listen actively as we have a set of objectives to be met.	4.45	Strongly Agree
5. The learners are able to identify solutions.	4.33	Strongly Agree
Average Mean	4.35	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.0-1.80)", Disagree (1.81-2.60)", Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40)", "Agree(3.41-4.20)", "Strongly Agree(4.21-5.0)"

Table 5 shows the effects of the play-based approach in terms of Problem-solving skills. As shown in the table, respondents agreed with the effects of the play-based approach, with a mean of 4.45.

The lowest weighted mean is indicator 1, with a mean of 4.28 . It also revealed that the grand mean of total respondents is 4.35 which means Strongly Agree.

Table 6. *Effects of Play-based Approach to the Academic performance of learners in terms of Knowledge Retention*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The learners can easily absorb information.	4.40	Strongly Agree
2. The learners are able to retain relevant concepts or topics.	4.48	Strongly Agree
3. The learners are capable of remembering and retrieving information.	4.37	Strongly Agree
4. Learners can gain familiarity with rules and concepts.	4.42	Strongly Agree
5. The learners can memorize and demonstrate mastery of certain skills such as reading.	4.43	Strongly Agree
Average Mean	4.42	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.0-1.80)", Disagree (1.81-2.60)", Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40)", "Agree(3.41-4.20)", "Strongly Agree(4.21-5.0)"

Table 6 shows the effects of the Play-based Approach. As shown in the table, respondents agreed that the learners are able to retain relevant concepts or topics with a mean of 4.48.

The lowest mean is indicator 3 because of the Play-based Approach. The learners are capable of remembering and retrieving information with a mean of 4.37. It also revealed that the average mean of total respondents is 4.42, which means Strongly Agree.

Table 7. *Effects of Play-based Approach to the Academic performance of learners in terms of Creativity in Performance*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The learners can think outside the box.	4.12	Agree
2. They become creative and active.	4.48	Strongly Agree
3. The learners can come up with unique approaches.	4.45	Strongly Agree
4. The learners have the ability to express themselves in a distinctive and imaginative manner while playing.	4.57	Strongly Agree
5. Learners were able establish new rules that can improve their performance	4.55	Strongly Agree
Average Mean	4.43	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.0-1.80)", Disagree (1.81-2.60)", Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40)", "Agree(3.41-4.20)", "Strongly Agree(4.21-5.0)"

Table 7 shows the effects of the Play-based Approach. As shown in the table, respondents agreed in indicator 5 that the learners are able to establish new rules that can improve their performance.

The lowest mean is indicator 1 which states that because of play-based approach , the learners can think outside the box with a mean of 4.12. It also revealed that the average mean of total respondents is 4.43, which means Strongly Agree.

Table 8. *Summary Table on the Effects of Play-based approach to Academic Performance of learners*

Effects Of Play-Based Approach	Average Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Language skills development	4.60	Strongly Agree
Problem-solving skills	4.35	Strongly Agree
Knowledge Retention	4.42	Strongly Agree
Creativity in Performance	4.43	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.45	Strongly Agree

Legend: "Strongly Disagree (1.0-1.80)", Disagree (1.81-2.60)", Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40)", "Agree(3.41-4.20)", "Strongly Agree(4.21-5.0)"

Table 8 summarizes the effects of the Play-based Approach on the academic performance of students. The results show that the highest contributing variable to the effect of the play-based approach on academic performance is language skills development, with a weighted mean of 4.60.

This confirms that most of the respondents agree on language skills development as an effect of the play-based approach. On the other hand, the lowest among the variables of effects of the play-based approach is problem-solving skills, with a weighted mean of 4.35.

Table 9. *Significant differences in the effects of the Play-based Approach to Academic Performance when respondents are grouped according to age*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
30-32	9	4.15				
33-35	7	4.5	4	0.511	0.05	Accept Ho
36-38	7	4.65				
39-41	8	4.6				
42 & above	29	4.5				

Table 9 displays that the calculated P-value is 0.511. At a significance level of 0.05 and 4 degrees of freedom. As the calculated H-value of 3.286 is less than the critical value and the P-value is greater than the significant level, the null hypothesis is accepted.

It indicates that there is no significant difference in the responses to the effects of the play-based approach on the academic performance of learners when grouped according to age.

This implies that respondents aged 30-42 years old and above have the same perceptions. The study indicates that any age can implement play-based in the classroom.

Table 10. *Significant differences in the factors contributing to the effects of play-based approach to Academic performance of learners students when grouped according to sex*

Groups	N	Median	df	P-value	Significant Level	Decision
Male	4	4.63	1	0.411	0.05	Accept Ho
Female	56	4.50				

Table 10 presents no significant differences in the effects of the play-based approach on the academic performance of learners when grouped according to sex. It shows the P value of 0.411 is greater than a significant level of 0.05, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the responses when grouped according to sex. This means that the groups of males and females have the same responses to the effects of a play-based approach to the academic performance of learners.

Table 11. *Significant difference of responses on the effects of play based approach to Academic performance of Learners when grouped according to length of work experience*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
1-3 years	3	3.85	4	0.120	0.05	Accept Ho
4-6 years	4	4.55				
7-9 years	7	4.65				
10-12 years	12	4.63				
More than 12 years	34	4.5				

Table 11 shows that the computed P-value is 0.120. Using 4 as the degree of freedom at a 0.05 level of significance, the P-value is greater than the significant level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is being accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the responses when grouped according to length of work experience. This infers that teachers have the same perceptions on the effects of a play-based approach on learners' academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Most of the respondents are female, forty-two years old and above, and Primary teachers with more than twelve years of experience or more.

Among the categories consisting of effects of the play-based approach, Language skills development gained the highest mean. Thus, it indicates that it affects the Academic Performance of learners as it helps learners acquire language. This was to conclude that teachers believe that the play-based approach has a significant effect on language skills development.

There is no significant difference in the effects of a play-based approach on the Academic Performance of learners when respondents are grouped according to age, sex, and length of work experience, which shows that the null hypothesis is accepted.

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were forwarded:

To the School Administrators, they may encourage teachers to incorporate Play-based Approach and conduct a seminar to strengthen teachers' capability to teach and assess literacy and numeracy.

To the Parents, they may guide and teach their children through play and do additional research on the activities suited for their children's learning.

To the Teachers, they may use or continue integrating play in various areas and create materials that can be used to enhance their problem-solving skills and creativity

To the learners, they may actively participate in any activities that can enhance their skills and maintain a positive perspective toward play-based pedagogy

To the Future Researchers, they may conduct a similar study and improve some flaws in Play-based method.

References

- Alvarez, C. (2020). The effects of a Play-Based instructional Approach on student' second language development in a dual language classroom. ResearchGate. <https://atcm.mathandtech.org/EP2020/contributed/21780.pdf>
- Bubikova-Moan, J., Hjetland, H. N., & Wollscheid, S. (2019). ECE teachers' views on play-based learning: a systematic review. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 27(6), 776–800. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293x.2019.1678717>
- Burgemeester, A. (2016, October 19). Jean Piaget's Theory of Play. *Psychologized*. <https://www.psychologized.org/jean-piagets-theory-of-play>

- Defining Play-based Learning | Encyclopedia on Early Childhood Development. (2018, February 1). Encyclopedia on Early Childhood Development. <https://www.child-encyclopedia.com/play-based-learning/according-experts/defining-play-based-learning>
- Frasson, C., Bamidis, P., & Vlamos, P. (2020). Brain function Assessment in learning: Second International Conference, BFAL 2020, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, October 9–11, 2020, Proceedings. Springer Nature.
- Harmat, L., Andersen, F. Ø., Ullén, F., Wright, J., & Sadlo, G. (2016). Flow experience: Empirical Research and Applications. Springer
- Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences. (2022). Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.14260/jemds>
- McArdle, J. (2023, September 11). Understanding Play Theories: A guide for play-based Teachers — My teaching cupboard. My Teaching Cupboard. <https://www.myteachingcupboard.com/blog/play-theories>
- Miller, C. L. (2021, May 12). Play theory. Pressbooks. <https://mlpp.pressbooks.pub/gamebasedlearning/chapter/play-theory/>
- Mohd Ismail, Rahida & Arshad, Rozita & Abas, Zakaria. (2018). Can Teachers' Age and Experience influence Teacher Effectiveness in HOTS?. International
- Mraz, K., Porcelli, A., & Tyler, C. (2016). Purposeful play: A Teacher's Guide to Igniting Deep and Joyful Learning Across the Day. Heinemann Educational Boo
- Nijhof et al., (2018). Healthy play, better coping: The importance of play for the development of children in health and disease. Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews, 95, 421–429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2018.09.024>
- Parker, R., Thomsen, B. S., & Berry, A. (2022). Learning Through Play at School – a framework for policy and practice. Frontiers Education, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2022.751801>
- Puteh, S.R. & Ali, Aliza. (2013). Preschool Teachers' Perceptions Towards the Use of Play- Based Approach in Language and Literacy Development for Preschool. Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction. 10. 79-98. 10.32890/mjli.10.2013.7652.
- Ronald et al.,(2016). English Language Proficiency and Academic Performance of Philippine Science High School Students International Journal of Languages, Literature and Linguistics,44-49 v1.2. - 10.18178/IJLL.2016.2.2.65
- Russ, S. W. (1998). Play, creativity, and adaptive functioning: Implications for play interventions. Journal of Clinical Child Psychology, 27(4), 469–480. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15374424jccp2704_11
- Sebastian, M., Banate, R., & Saquin, M. (2022). GENDER ROLES AMONG PUBLIC ELEMENTARY TEACHERS: BASIS FOR GENDER-RESPONSIVE INTERVENTION ACTIVITIES. International Online Journal of Primary Education, 11(2), 401–411. <https://doi.org/10.55020/iojpe.1222199>
- Singha, S., Warr, M., Mishra, P., & Henriksen, D. (2020) Playing with Creativity Across the Lifespan: a Conversation with Dr. Sandra Russ. TechTrends, 64(4), 550–554. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-020-00514-3>
- Tai, Heang,et al..(2021) Play-based Learning: A Qualitative Report on How Teachers Integrate Play in the Classroom
- Taylor, M. E., & Boyer, W. (2019). Play-Based Learning: Evidence-Based research to improve children's learning experiences in the kindergarten classroom. Early Childhood Education Journal, 48(2), 127–133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-019-00989-7>

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